

Validation of three names of families in the *Pucciniomycotina*

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Abstract. Three names of families in the *Pucciniomycotina*, *Spiculogloeaceae*, *Erythrobasidiaceae*, and *Naohideaceae*, are validated.

Key words: *Erythrobasidiaceae*, *Naohideaceae*, *Pucciniomycotina*, *Spiculogloeaceae*, taxonomy

Recently, a new classificatory system of the *Pucciniomycotina* has been proposed by Bauer *et al.* (2006). Among the newly described higher taxa, there are three names of orders, formed as descriptive names [ICBN, Vienna Code, Art. 16.1.(b)]: *Spiculogloeales* R. Bauer *et al.*, *Erythrobasidiales* R. Bauer *et al.*, and *Naohideales* R. Bauer *et al.* For these orders, families were not recognized or included. Herein, validation of the names for the three missing families is proposed.

***Spiculogloeaceae* Denchev, fam. nov.**

MYCOBANK # 515111

Fungi Agaricostilbomycetum cellulis haustorialibus tremelloideis.
Genus typicus: Spiculogloea P. Roberts, *Mycotaxon* **60**: 112 (1996).

Members of the *Agaricostilbomycetes* having tremelloid haustorial cells — characters given by Bauer *et al.* (2006: 45) for the *Spiculogloeales* R. Bauer, Begerow, J.P. Samp., M. Weiß & Oberw.

***Erythrobasidiaceae* Denchev, fam. nov.**

MYCOBANK # 515112

Fungi Cystobasidiomycetum systemate coenzymatis Q10 hydrogenato.
Genus typicus: Erythrobasidium Hamam., Sugiy. & Komag., *Journal of General and Applied Microbiology, Tokyo* **34**: 285 (1988).

Members of the *Cystobasidiomycetes* having a hydrogenated Coenzyme Q10 system — characters given by Bauer *et al.* (2006: 46) for the *Erythrobasidiales* R. Bauer, Begerow, J.P. Samp., M. Weiß & Oberw.

The type species of *Erythrobasidium*, *E. hasegawae* (Y. Yamada & Komag.) Hamam., Sugiy. & Komag., was described as an anamorphic species (Hamamoto *et al.* 1988). On its base, *E. hasegawianum* Hamam., Sugiy. & Komag. was described as a teleomorphic name (Hamamoto *et al.* 1991; cfr also Bai *et al.* 2001). Later on, the proposed basidial stage of *E. hasegawianum* was found to be a conidial stage (Sampaio *et al.* 1999; Aime *et al.* 2006).

***Naohideaceae* Denchev, fam. nov.**

MYCOBANK # 515113

Fungi Cystobasidiomycetum haustoriis intracellularibus.
Genus typicus: Naohidea Oberw., *Report of the Tottori Mycological Institute* **28**: 114 (1990).

Members of the *Cystobasidiomycetes* forming intracellular haustoria — characters given by Bauer *et al.* (2006: 46–47) for the *Naohideales* R. Bauer, Begerow, J.P. Samp., M. Weiß & Oberw.

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